

THE ROLE OF PHRASEOLOGY IN TEACHING AND LEARNING ENGLISH

Akbarova Mohinur Alisher qizi

Fergana State University, Uzbekistan, Fergana

Annotation: Teaching phraseology in foreign teaching methodology plays a significant role in forming vocabulary and lingua-cultural competence of students as phraseological units encapsulate a national, country’s cultural outlook. In this article, we try to define phraseological concepts in teaching and learning English and discuss the formation of phraseological units.

Key words: Phraseology, phraseological units, vocabulary, words, definition, language, phrase, formation of phraseological units.

In linguistics, phraseology is defined as a science of various fixed expressions, word combinations like idioms, phrases, phrasal verbs and other kinds of multi-word lexical segments of a language. According to Hoey and Romer, lexis and syntax, or vocabulary (phraseology as a part of vocabulary) and grammar, are traditionally viewed as discrete aspects of language in teaching (Hoey, 2005; Romer, 2009). Phraseology (from Greek —phrasis, “way of speaking” and —logia, “study of”) is a scholarly approach to language which was developed in twentieth century. According Merriam Webster’s dictionary, the term phraseology came from new Latin Phraseologia and means a manner of organizing words and phrases into longer elements: style and choice of words. Macmillan Dictionary defines phraseology a particular way of putting words together to express something. And it explains phraseology as terminology as it denotes the words and phrases used in a particular profession. Oxford English Dictionary defines term phraseology as uncountable and formal noun that means the particular way in which words and phrases are arranged when saying or writing something. Wikipedia notes that it studies phraseological

constructions and segments in a particular language. However, the Macmillan English Dictionary and Oxford English Dictionary open its meaning as words and phrases used in a particular profession and putting words and phrases together to convey meaning while uttering or noting something. Uzbek linguistics defines phraseology as a science that studies phrases, set phrases, even proverbs and sayings. And we can say the function of phraseology of every language is to study phrases, multi-word language units with their direct as well indirect meanings that make language vivid and colourful. Charles Bally, (1865 -1947) Swiss linguist who was the founder of the theory of phraseology, first systematized combination of the words in 13 his books "style Essay" and "French style". He included a chapter on the phraseology in his books in style. [43.4] In the first book Charles Bally distinguished four groups of phrases:

1) free combinations (les groupements libres), ie combinations deprived of stability, decaying after their formation;

2) usual combinations (les groupements usuels), ie phrases with otnositelnosvobodnoy communication components, allowing some changes, for example, une grave maladie - a serious disease (une dangereuse, serieuse maiaidie - risk of serious diseases); [2.p.60]

3) phraseological series (les series phraseologiques), ie groups of words. In which two concepts ryadopolozhnyh almost merge into one. The stability of these revolutions is fixed by primary usage, for example, remporter une viktoire - win, (courir un danger -endangered These combinations allow the regrouping of the components.;

4) phraseological unity (les unites phraseologiques), ie combinations in which the words have lost their meaning and express a united indecomposable concept. These combinations do not allow the regrouping of the components.

This, combinations of words Bally distinguishes the degree of stability by: coupling in which there is freedom of categories of components, and combinations thereof, devoid of such freedom. Bally is only schematically outlined these groups,

but did not give them any detail description. In his later work, "French style" Bally is considered the usual combinations and phraseological ranks as intermediate types of phrases and distinguishes only two groups of combinations: a combination of free and phraseological unity that phrases components are permanently employed in these combinations to express the same thought. The question of phraseology as a linguistic discipline was first brought by outstanding linguist Professor E.D. Polivanova. E.D. Polivanov believed that the phraseology "take apart and stable position (like phonetics, morphology, etc.) in the linguistic literature of the future - when in sequential staged various problems our science lacks, will be random gaps." E.D. Polivanova foresight carried out today. The question of phraseology as a linguistic discipline was also studied by V.V. Vinogradov. His works contributed to the emergence of many works on the phraseology of different languages. Such a systematic accumulation of facts - one of the prerequisites for the creation of phraseology as a linguistic discipline [3.p.25] Studying phraseology is characterized not only by the number of publications, but also their character. Among them are many monographs, doctoral and master's theses, collections of articles on phraseology, phraseological dictionaries, bibliographies. Not to mention the numerous conferences and meetings on issues of phraseology. This there is every reason to note the rapid growth of phraseological research in our country. Kunin A.V. phraseological units classified according to how they are formed. He pointed to the primary and secondary ways of formation of phraseological units. The primary way of formation of phraseological units are those when the unit is based on freedom of speech Group:

a) the most productive in modern English is the formation of phraseological units by transferring the meaning of the terminology of the word groups, for example, we can mention the following phrase in space technology: «launching pad» в его терминологической смысле — «стартовая площадка», в его передаваемых смысле — «отправная точка», «to link up»-«стикуватися, стыковать

космические челноки «в его переоборудовали смысле это означает»
знакомиться

b) a large group of phraseological units formed from free speech groups by converting their meaning, such as «Granny farm» — «пансионат для фуршета стариков»;

c) phraseological units can be formed by alliteration, «A sad sack» — «несчастный случай», «culture vulture» — «человек, который интересуется искусством», «fudge and nudge» — «уклончивость».

d) can be created with the help of expression, particularly characteristic of the formation of interjections, such as My aunt - «Моя тетя!», «слышать, слышать».

e) they can be created with the help of the group distorts words such as Odds and ends «Мелочи» was formed from the "odd ends", «нечетные заканчивается»,

f) that can be created using archaisms, eg » " In brown study " - ' - ' в коричневый исследование“ means " in gloomy meditation «в мрачной медитации» "where both components retain their archaic values

f) They may be created by other proposals in the field of life, for example: That cock will not fight «это петух не будет бороться " can be used as a free word group when it is used in sports (fighting cock), he becomes a phraseological units when it is used in everyday life, because it is used metaphorically

g) they can be created when we use some of the unrealistic images, such as "To have butterflies in the stomach" «have butterflies in the stomach" - "experience the excitement», «to have green fingers" - to achieve success gardeners "

h) they can be created with the help of expression of writers or politicians in everyday life, such as "Corridors of power" (Snow) - «corridors of power», «American dream» (Alby) - «the American dream», «locust years» (Churchil) - "locust years», «the winds of change» «wind of change" (Mk Millan).

The English language is full of phraseological units. Obviously, idioms, phrases, phrasal verbs and set expressions, aphorisms, maxims, proverbs and sayings are the main units of any language and without them our language may seem shallow

or boring. Such linguistic units play an active role in our speech, language and culture, they make the language and speech colourful as well as attractive. Time by time they are being developed and polished. It is impossible not to mention about these units while learning the language. However, students may face difficulties in differing these terms from each other. Let us consider them briefly. A phrase is a group of related words that do not include subject-verb relationship. From syntactical viewpoint no matter how many words the phrase consists of, all the elements are regarded as a single unit. Phrases may be of different kinds. Examples: The pretty and clever girl — noun phrase. My favorite football player, best goal keeper, Ignatij Nesterov have been playing for Uzbekistan’s combined team for a long times

— appositive phrase

I cannot find the books that I put on the shelf yesterday — prepositional phrase

An idiom like a phrase is a group of words. However, the most distinguishing feature of an idiom is that its meaning is hardly predictable as the meaning of the idiom stays far from the lexical meaning of the components of the idiom.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, we can say that phraseology as an individual part of linguistics should be carefully and profoundly studied by language learners as phrases, set expressions, idioms as well as fixed sayings are widely used in both written and oral speech in any language, particularly in English. In other words, we believe that the EFL learner must study the phraseology - phraseological units, their origin, characteristics and usage, cultural specifics, etc. - in order to speak fluently and accurately as well as understand thoroughly as a native speaker for it helps the EFL students to make a complex speech and feel confident.

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